

CAUSES OF INFERTILITY IN MEN AND WOMEN

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ABSTRACT

Infertility is a disease of the reproductive system which effects in couples men and women. The couple is generally considered clinically infertile when pregnancy has not occurred after at least twelve months of regular unprotected sexual activity. Therefore, knowing the prevalence of infertility is important and can be effective in decision making. The aim of this study to know their lives and to study and prevent the cause of infertility among infertile female and male.

Infertility (Lat. Sterilitas) - in medicine - the inability of the pair in childbearing age to conceive a child with regular sexual life . A married couple is considered fruitless if the pregnancy of a woman does not occur during the year of regular sexual life (sexual contacts are no less than 2 times a week) without the use of means and methods of contraception. According to the World Health Organization " About 8% of married couples during the reproductive period of life are faced with infertility problem". The person distinguishes the absolute infertility, predetermined by incurable changes in the sexual apparatus of men or women (defects of development, operational removal of germ, injury and other), and relative, the reasons for which can be Eliminated. Infertility is called primary if pregnancy has never been, and secondary, if a woman earlier had at least one pregnancy, whatever she ended (childbirth, ectopic pregnancy, miscarriage, etc.). Female infertility is striking about 8-10% of all couples. Women's factors can cause a couple of vapor in 30-40% of cases. It was found that men's factors are the cause of infertility at about 30% of cases. Another 30-40% of the steam both female and male factors contribute to the vapor of the couple. Approximately 5-10% of vapor vapor remains inexplicable even after the examination. The structure of the reasons for infertility in 100 married couples (200 people) suffering from infertility, in Tashkent and the Tashkent region (50 families) was studied. It has been established that among the examined women in the genesis of infertility, hormonal dysfunction occupies the main place, as well as inflammatory diseases of the urogenital system (diffuse goiter with subclinical hypothyroidism, ovarian failure With a disruption of menstrual function, polycystic ovarian syndrome, hyperandrogenation, lack of lutein phase, follicleogenesis disruption, and infection). Among the examined men in the genesis of infertility, hormonal dysfunction (androgenic

deficiency associated with excess body weight, spermatogenesis, hypergonadotropic and Hypogonadotropic hypogonadism).

Infertility is divided into male and female. Therefore, the causes, diagnosis and methods of treatment differ.

To basic reasons, infertility in women include:

- Ovulation - hormonal imbalance;
- Dysfunction of ovaries;
- The uterine pipes, spikes;
- Polycystosis of the ovaries;
- Premature climax;
- Obstructions in the cervical canal; -
- Development and structure of the uterus;
- Iatrogenic injuries;
- endometriosis;
- Syndrome unexploded follicle;

immunological infertility (due to the presence of antibodies to spermatozoa in the body of the woman).

Age for women .

Age remains the most important factor affecting the ability to have a child. With age, the fertility is naturally reduced. The decrease begins for a woman aged 30 years, and the greatest decline is observed after 35 years. The main reason for this trend - with age in the female organism, ripens almost 3 times less than follicles, and the quality of the eggs themselves is significantly deteriorated. In addition, the low quality of female sex cells often leads not only to the unaccompanied pregnancy, as well as to spontaneous miscarriages or the birth of a baby with various genetic deviations. The uterus, the presence of known or diagnosed anomalies of the uterus usually means that you are likely to experience such states like myomas, polyps or endometriosis that can lead to the formation of scar tissue or adhesions, even after they were cured earlier. The cervix sometimes is detected in the mucous membrane of a woman's uterus, which can actually go into the attack, killing sperm before it appears a chance to go to the waiting position. This is a hostile cervical mucus and can be caused by infection in the lower deposits of the reproductive path or increased acidity.

Matrix

The presence of known or diagnosed uterine anomalies usually means that you will probably have experiences such as myoma, polyps or endometriosis that can lead to the formation of scar or adhesions, even after they were cured earlier.

The reasons for infertility in men men's infertility practically does not appear, which is why there was an erroneous opinion that fruitlessly women are.

Factors leading to infertility in men:

- Weakness and viability of spermatozoa;
- Secondary reduction of their quantity;
- Food Promotion of spermatozoa for seeding channels and the release of them outwards;
- Hypospadias, lack of and obstruction of the seedy ways;

- infectious inflammatory diseases of the urogenital system;
- Surrigic manipulations (pelvis hernia, operation on the bladder, etc.);
- Outbreaks of other organism systems (liver cirrhosis, tuberculosis, diabetes, infectious vapotitis with a complication of orchitis, chronic renal failure);
- development of sexual function;
- Ityogenic infertility;
- Endocrine disorders.

Spermatooids

The low number of spermatozoa, a bad mobility of spermatozoa or an abnormal form can reduce your ability to fertilize the egg. A low number of spermatozois is noted in cases when a man is less than

million spermatozois on a milliliter of sperm. Mobility of spermatozoa is the ability of spermatozoa to steadily move (or swim) d to bald down the egg. An anomalous size or shape of spermatozoa can affect the ability to reach and fertilize the egg. Fragmentation of the sperm DNA.

Hormones

If you have a state at which the levels of the lute-reducing hormone (LH) and the follicle-empty hormone (FSG) decrease, this can lead to low production of spermatozoa or reduce the testosterone level in the blood.

Age

is not only a female reproductive function, but also a men's, may decline with age. This can affect the course of pregnancy, the risk of miscarriage and the general state of your child's health.

Additional reasons include: the negative effect of

- alcohol and nicotine
- various injuries of the sexual apparatus
- work in adverse conditions
- stress
- violation of labor and recreation.

Treatment of male infertility as in women, before, to improve the spermatogenic function - appointment medicinal therapy. Often prescribed preparations that stimulate blood supply to the genital organs, vitamins, hormone, the balanced nutrition. The obstructive form of infertility in men is treated by holding a biopsy - during the operation is recovered mature spermatozoids from the egg and its attributes. The rehabilitation period lasts in a hospital of 10-12 days, during which the physical loads, sexual contact, overwork and stressful situations are excluded.

Take care of yourself! And remember, the main health of the health is a timely handling for help with a specialist!

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